

Notes

CNDO/2 Calculations on the Percentage of cis-trans Isomers in Some Thioamides

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THE cis-isomer predominates in secondary thioamides compared to the corresponding amides. This may be due to the large size of the sulphur atom in comparison to oxygen atom. Recently, Walter and Kubersky^{1,2} have carried out extensive spectroscopic studies on thioamides and thioformanilides. They have studied the electronic, steric and conformational properties, intramolecular hydrogen bonding and cis-trans isomerism in thioamides and thioformanilides from the frequencies and the relative intensities of the NH-stretching vibration bands of primary and secondary thioamides in carbon-tetrachloride solutions. In the present studies, we have tested the validity of CNDO/2 method^{3,4} and of the equation (I)

$$\frac{N_{trans}}{N_{cis}} = \exp(-\Delta E/RT) \quad \dots (I)$$

$$\% \text{ of trans-isomer} = \frac{N_{trans}}{N_{cis} + N_{trans}} \times 10^2 \quad \dots (II)$$

for determining the cis-trans ratio in thioamides. In equation (I), ΔE is the energy difference between the cis and trans isomers. The value of ΔE was calculated by CNDO/2 method^{3,4} and the results are given in Table I. Using $R = 1.9869 \text{ cal/}^\circ\text{K/mole}$ and at $T = 25^\circ (298^\circ\text{K})$, the percentage of trans isomer determined by equation (II) is given in Table I.

TABLE I: PERCENTAGE OF CIS-TRANS ISOMERS IN SOME THIOAMIDES

Molecule	ΔE (Kcal/mole)	% of trans isomer	
		Calc.	Obs. (^{1,2})
N-Methylthioformamide	-1.40	91	93.5
N-Ethylthioformamide	-1.22	88	88.0
N-Propylthioformamide	-1.22	88	86.5
N-Isopropylthioformamide	-1.06	84	79.5
N-Butylthioformamide	-0.84	81	87.0
N-Isobutylthioformamide	-0.78	79	78.0

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It is quite evident from Table I that there is a good agreement between the experimental and theoretical values and hence the validity of the CNDO/2 method and equation (I) for determining the cis-trans ratios in these systems is established.

References

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Co(II) with Ethylene diamine & Propylene diamine

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COBALT(II) yields Co(II) Pyrrolidone which on further coordination with ethylene diamine and propylene diamine gives mixed ligand complexes. The complexes after isolation and purification have been studied and their structures elucidated using spectro photometric and magnetic data supported by conductivity and molecular weight measurements. General methods for preparation have been discussed in literature¹⁻³.

Experimental data of complexes have been summarised in the table given below. The calculated values of percentages of Co, N and mol.wts., on basis of elemental analysis have been shown in parentheses against their respective experimental values.

Results and Discussion

Visible spectral data of complexes and molar extinction coefficient values support the tetrahedral structure of complexes^{4,5}. Magnetic moment values lie in the range 4.4-4.8 B.M. which is the reported range for tetrahedral Co(II) complexes^{6,7}.

In pyrrolidone molecule there are two possibilities of coordination, one from N atom and the other from carbonyl group with the opening of the double bond. Structural limitations do not allow the attachment of Co(II) with C=O group. According to Lewis concept 'N' with a lone pair of electrons possesses greater possibility of coordination with metal atom. From i.r. data it has been noted that the C=O

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